

Gandhi and Education for Peace

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A B S T R A C T

Man and woman are of equal rank but they are not identical. They are a peeler was pair being supplementary to one another; each helps the other, so that without the one the existence of the other cannot be conceived, and therefore it follows as a necessary corollary from these facts that anything that will impair the status of either of them will involve the equal ruin of them both. In framing any scheme of women's education this cardinal truth must be constantly kept in mind. Man is supreme in the outward activities of a married pair and, therefore, it is in the fitness of things that he should have a greater knowledge thereof. On the other hand, home life is entirely the sphere of women and, therefore, in domestic affairs, in the upbringing and education of children, women ought to have more knowledge.

A society or a group, which depends partly or wholly on state aid for the existence of its religion, goes not deserve, or, better still, does not have any religion worth the name. A curriculum of religious instruction should include a study of the tenets of faiths other than one's own. For this purpose the students should be trained to cultivate the habit of understanding and appreciating the doctrines tolerance. This if properly done would help to give them a spiritual assurance and a better appreciation of their own religion... There is one rule, however, which should always be kept in mind while studying all great religions and that is, that one should study them only through the writings of known votaries of the respective religions.

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Introduction

One of the most significant aspects of the multi-faceted Gandhi is that which refers to education. Gandhi believed that the most effective means for political, social and cultural changes that he proposed was education. Some of his “Experiments with Truth” transform constantly into educative experiments of community life. His Autobiography reviews and evaluates them. The first experiment took place in south Africa in 1904, followed by another more comprehensive one in the Tolstoy Farm in South Africa in 1910, and finally in the Satyagraha Ashram at Sabarmati in India, near Ahmedabad and in Sevagram, not very far from Wardha. In his first book, Hind Swaraj Gandhi devoted a chapter specifically to education.

The theme recurs in the pages of Gandhi periodicals Young India and Harijan till it reaches the national conference on education. In the Wardha Plan, the educative method of Gandhi was reflected in good measure which he called Naitalim.

In the same way he fought against the prejudices that marginalised women. In his ashram, boys and girls, men and women, lived together. Gandhi exalted the women by calling them “the best part of humanity”. He vindicated the equality of sexes even while acknowledging the diversities imposed by nature. He asked women to take part in social life and was convinced that his policy of non-violence was more easily followed by women than ny men, owing to their greater capacity for sacrifice.

Ashram Education

In the Ashram, Hindus, Muslims, Christians, and Sikhs were urged to live peacefully. Gandhi inculcated respect for all religions. “Every human being”, wrote Gandhi “constituted a partial revelation of the Truth. If we see everybody on a plane of equality, we will not hesitate to introduce each acceptable aspect of other religions in our faith. The true knowledge of religion breaks the barriers between faiths.” If I am a Hindu I should behave like a brother with the Muslims and other believers. I should not differentiate between people with distinct beliefs.

It is not surprising then that in this way, Gandhi could write that “All the inmates of the Tolstoy Farm considered each other as members of the same family,” He reaches the same conclusion when he

speaks of the early days of the Sabarmati Ashram: “We were some twenty-five persons, men and women from different parts of India, including five young Tamilians who had accompanied me from south Africa. We all lived together lived together like one family.

The Roots of Peace

It is imperative that each one of us should become the master of ourselves in order to defeat all tendencies of violence within us. He referred to the classical prohibitions and proposed them as oaths to be taken by the senses. Gandhi does not hide the difficulties that one must overcome in order to fulfil these vows. “The path to self-purification is slow and difficult” writes Gandhi in the last page of his autobiography. To achieve total purity, it is necessary to absolutely destroy the elements related to passion which are embedded in our thoughts, words and deeds; to be above the varying emotions of love and hate, attraction and repulsion. It occurs to me that the control of the most subtle of passions and desires, is more difficult than the conquest of the world with weapons.

A Programme of Action

Gandhi always maintained that non-violence was not for cowards. It requires being “ready for sacrifice” adhere strongly to truth”, “doing away with any fear regarding the loss of goods, false honours, relatives and life itself cowardice is worse than violence and makes man an incapable and useless being.” Strength does not arise from physical prowess but from an “indomitable will”. Those who practise violence, like the soldiers in war ready for anything and likewise should be those who want to practise non-violence.

Another pledge-the seventh one, is related to manual work according to the capacity and aptitude of each one. This was one of his favourite themes. He said that work was a means of strengthening the body, acquiring an integral education which goes beyond mere knowledge,

bring about equality among all, promote common welfare and a spirit of service, affirm the superiority of man as a person in the face of an excessive and robotizing technology”. “The hand is one of the gifts that differentiate man from animals.”

Swadeshi” is the name given to the eighth pledge which means defence of the native traditions and things. It is essential to keep in mind the political and social context of Gandhi’s times i.e. an India culturally and politically dominated by England. Education for peace, for sacrifice, for renunciation should not have meant an unconditional giving up or a loss of one’s own national and cultural identity.”

While being open to the world Gandhi postulates the great principle: one should go to the universal through the particular. “Helping and serving the people around you is actually helping the world”

And around Gandhi was India with its history, its literature, its traditions and its languages. Gandhi saw it humiliated and exploited and thus proceeded to act against a ruling class comprising of English men and Indians, who wanted to “anglicize India”, imposing a foreign language and customs. “By receiving an English style of education, we have enslaved the nation and betrayed the historical, ethnic and social traditions of the country”. He therefore wanted Hindi to be taught as the future national language along with one of the 15 regional languages. This was to ensure that the child does not feel “a stranger in his own house” and through the language comes in contact with the entire cultural heritage.

Parents and Teachers

We have till now followed the eleven vows that Gandhi put forward as the basis of his communities and which synthesized his educative programme, for achieving peaceful coexistence.

There clearly appears the importance that Gandhi confers on community life. “Non-violence cannot be inculcated by an isolated person, one requires a community in which the individual can prove his capacity to face and overcome all difficulties.”

For Gandhi the first community was the family. In that the parents should educate the children with world and examples. The state, rendering its function by way of compulsory primary education, weakened the power of the parents. To minimise the harm it is necessary that those in charge of education maintain constant contact with the parents and above all, make the school a kind of family according to the above mentioned programme.

Gandhi outlined in his writings the ideal picture of the teacher and kept coming back repeatedly to this theme. He knew very well that the efficient education for peace, depended in a good measure, on them. They should establish a “contact with the heart” of their students; know them individually, encourage them to be active members of the society, although their state of studentship impedes them from a true political commitment and educate them for self-rule. The teacher should become a constant source of learning for his students.”

Spiritual Education

The final aspect of Gandhi’s educative programme is religious. It did not form part of the eleven basic vows of the community, but it was automatically understood as it formed part of the general atmosphere in which all activities took place.

Gandhi did not want a confessional religious education but a presentation of the basic universal ethics. All religions were to be respected with a firm faith in God “having known that strength comes from God and not from us, and violence triumphs only when there is a lack of genuine faith in God”.

In the chapter of his Autobiography entitled, “Spiritual Education”, he writes: “Education without spiritual culture is of no use and can even cause harm. Perfection, the absence of error, absolute control on thought etc. are impossible without total devotion to God and his grace.”

Evaluation

Gandhi's ideas on education got a chance of being put into practice on an experimental level beyond his ashrams, in the various provinces of India, after the Wardha Educational conference in 1937. In 1940 the initial programme that constituted "Basic Education" for

children was extended by Gandhi to include adolescents and adults. The central point of these experiments was teaching through manual work. It was conceived not only as having creative, but productive, value in order to achieve a self-sufficient economy for students and teachers alike. The conflict with the government during the Second World War, Gandhi's prolonged imprisonment and the lack of teachers with a spirit of service affected the results of these experiments.

After the attainment of independence and Gandhi's death some Nai Talim schools continued functioning on an experimental level, but their introduction on the national level was considered Utopian. Factors such as the emphasis on productive work with an eye on the development of the local handicrafts, the seeming rejection of western culture and modernity, adversely affected the expansion of the project. Nevertheless, it continued in small communities in India thanks to the outstanding follower of Gandhi's ideals, namely, Vinoba Bhave, and in the West through the community of the Ark founded by another great disciple of Gandhi, Lanza del Vasto.

If it is true that the educative project of Gandhi is unlikely to be adopted on a national level, it contains the crux of the principles that constitute the soul of all sound education. These are: an integral education overcoming social, racial and religious barriers, joint participation of students and teachers, in activities of the school, and emphasis on ethical principles.

Hind Swaraj

Hind Swaraj is the seed from which the tree of Gandhian thought has grown to its full stature. For those interested in Gandhi's thought in a general way, it is the right place to start, for it is here that he presents his basic ideas in their proper relationship to one another. And for those who wish to study his thought more methodically, it remains the norm by which to assess the theoretical significance of his other writings, including the Autobiography. It can also save them from the danger of otherwise getting drowned in the vast sea of Gandhian anthologies.

The very composition of Hind Swaraj has something of the heroic about it. It was written in ten days, between 13 and 22 November, 1909, on board the ship Kildonan Castle on the

author's return trip from England to South Africa, after what proved to be an abortive lobbying mission to London. The whole manuscript was written on the ship's stationery, and the writing went on at such a furious pace that when the right hand got tired, Gandhi continued with the left forty of the 275 manuscript pages were written by the left hand. And he wrote as if under inspiration. In the entire autograph, only sixteen lines have been scratched out and only a few words changed here and there (Prabhudas Gandhi 1957, 87-8).

Gandhi's Intentions

First of all the question of an inner illumination and the consequent urge to communicate.

Secondly, he wanted to clarify the meaning of swaraj, the concept that provides the theoretical framework of the book. This is done by introducing a distinction between swaraj as self-government or the quest for home rule or the good state, and swaraj as self-rule or the quest for self-improvement.

Thirdly, he felt it necessary to respond specifically to the ideology of political terrorism adopted by the expatriates. The book was written in order to show that they were following 'a suicidal policy'. He recalled in 1921 how on his 1909 visit to London he had come into contact with 'every known Indian anarchist' there, and how he had wanted to write a book 'in answer to the Indian school of violence'.

Fourthly, Gandhi was anxious to teach the Indians that 'modern civilisation' posed a greater threat to them than did colonialism. They appeared to him to take it for granted that modern civilisation was an unmixed blessing, and colonialism an unmixed evil, forgetting that colonialism itself was a product of modern civilisation.

Fifthly, he wanted to contribute towards the reconciliation of Indians and Britons. This is evident from the 'exhortation' to 'the English' in chapter xx. Modern civilisation posed as much a problem for them as it did for the Indians. 'At heart you belong to a religious nation',

Finally, Gandhi believed that through Hind Swaraj he would be able to give Indians a practical philosophy, an updated conception of dharma, that would fit them for life in the modern world.

In the past dharma was tied to a hierarchical system of duties and obligations and to the preservation of status.

Historical Context: Modern Civilization

Modern civilization forms the broad historical context of Hind Swaraj. Its critique of that civilization is one of its main contributions to modern political thought. In historical terms, it is Gandhi's apprehensions about certain tendencies in modern civilisation that made him the thinker and the political innovator that he is. The tone of his criticism is sometimes harsh and intemperate and is likely to mislead the reader. It is all the more necessary therefore to say at once that his attitude towards modern civilization, though critical, is not wholly negative. Being critical implies the desire to improve the object criticised. So it is with Gandhi and modern civilization. Thus he welcomes a number of its contributions—civil liberty, equality, rights, prospects for improving the economic conditions of life, liberation of women from tradition, and religious toleration. At the same time, the welcome is conditional in that liberty has to harmonise with swaraj, rights with duties, empirical knowledge with moral insight, economic development with spiritual progress, religious toleration with religious belief, and women's liberation with the demands of a broader conception of humanity.

Gandhi's admiration for the British constitution helps to put his attitude towards colonialism in its right perspective. In his Autobiography he speaks of the two passions of his life the passion for loyalty to the British constitution and the passion for nursing (CW 39 :140-3). The history of British rule is the history of constitutional evolution.

Gandhi has his own definition of civilisation : civilisation is 'that mode of conduct which points out to man the path of duty' (sudharo, ch. XIII). Barbarism (kudharo) is the absence of civilisation. By modern or Western civilisation (he often used these terms interchangeably) he meant that 'mode of conduct' which emerged from the Enlightenment, and more exactly, from the Industrial Revolution. 'Let it be remembered', he wrote in 1908, that western civilisation is only a hundred years old, or to be more precise, fifty' (CW 8: 374). The Industrial Revolution for him was much more than a mere change in the mode of production. As he interprets it, it brought into being a new mode of life, embracing a people's outlook on nature and human nature,

religion, ethics, science, knowledge, technology, politics and economics. According to this outlook, nature was taken to be an autonomous entity operating according to its own laws, something to be mastered and possessed at will for the satisfaction of human needs, desires and political ambitions. This outlook brought about an epistemological revolution which in turn paved the way for the secularisation of political theory. The satisfaction of the desire for economic prosperity came to be identified as the main object of politics. Religion, when it was not dismissed as mere superstition, was valued only for its social and psychological use. The Industrial Revolution altered the concept of labour, now accepted mainly for its ability to produce profit, power and capital. Manual labour was looked upon as fit only for the unlettered and the backward. With the technological revolution that followed the industrial revolution, machines, hitherto allies of humans, seemed to assert their autonomy.

Modern political theory provided the general ethical framework within which the changes occurring in the scientific, technological and economic fields were to be integrated. Two types of political theory emerged, one for the industrialised societies and the other for the rest of the world. Liberalism and liberal institutions were thought appropriate for industrialised societies; imperialism and colonialism for the non-industrialised societies such as India. By the third quarter of the nineteenth century, the world for all practical purposes was divided into the industrialised and the non-industrialised, or the 'civilised' and the 'non-civilised', parts. Even the saint of liberalism, J. S. Mill, accepted this civilisational partition of the world. He would in all sincerity use the very doctrine of liberty to justify imperial rule over India.

Conclusion

A philosophy of education is not just an amalgam of isolated bits of prescriptions regarding teaching, learning, and preparation of syllabi etc. It is a coherent account of the concepts of man, society, teaching and learning, and the needs and requirements of individual and society at large. Seen in this light, one comes across a profound philosophy of education in Gandhi. Similarly, we do not need a group of well-trained ecologists to tell us that every attempt should be made to protect the ecological balance. Any programme of social reconstruction must start with identifying the need of the individual and the society vis-a-vis that of the environment.

The accumulated insight and wisdom of the society through the centuries comes to our rescue in this regard. We do not need money, men and time in order to sort out and tell ourselves what are the needs of the hour. In the contemporary period, not only in India but also throughout the world over, a major chunk of the educational budget is being consumed simply to identify the need of man. Gandhi will treat these educational programmes and endeavours as futile and barren. Our arguments may seem very simplistic. But anyone having some idea of the way national wealth is being consumed by funding absurd research projects throughout the country one is simply forced to this conclusion.

In any scheme of social reconstruction education plays an important role and no educational scheme is complete unless it takes into account the legitimate needs and aspirations of men in society. These needs and aspirations are to be sacred in nature, in that their espousal should not in any way inflict pain and suffering on others in any form at all. Gandhi was a conventionalist in the sense that he turned to the scriptures, the ancient wisdom, and love handed down to humanity from time immemorial. All that is conventional need not be rejected as antiquarian and old-fashioned. Conventional wisdom in matters of morals is to be respected. In matters of education these conventional morals are to be respected. Gandhi's conventionalism in this regard should not be treated as a case of old-fashioned obscurantism.

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